

Assessment of the prevalence of Depression among Insulin and Oral Hypoglycemic Users with Diabetes and Associated Factors in Addis Ababa Public Hospitals: A Comparative Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Diabetes Mellitus (DM), particularly type 2 diabetes is a prevalent non-communicable disease with a significant association with depression. Alongside diabetes, depression is a common comorbidity that significantly impacts patients' quality of life and disease management. The estimated prevalence of depression among diabetic patients in Ethiopia was 39.73%, and its subgroup analysis showed that the prevalence is about 52.9% in Addis Ababa.

Objective: The main objective of this study is to assess the prevalence and associated factors of depression among insulin and oral hypoglycemic medication users with Diabetes Mellitus in public hospitals of Addis Ababa.

Methods: A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted in three selected public hospitals in Addis Ababa among 422 randomly selected study participants from October 1 2024, to November 30 2024. Data were collected, entered, and cleaned by Epi Info 7 and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics for categorical variables were presented in frequencies and percentages, and mean and inter-quartile range were used to describe continuous variables. Then, bivariate logistic regression analysis was performed for each independent variable regarding the presence of depression among DM patients. An adjusted odd ratio (AOR) with 95% confidence interval was used to identify associated variables for depression, and p-values < 0.05 were considered to indicate statistical significance.

Results : The prevalence of depression among DM patient was 54.27%(95% CI:49.4%-59.1%), and the prevalence of depression was 44.9% among DM participants taking oral hypoglycemic agents and 63.4% among insulin users (eventhough the difference in their mean depression scale score (8.54 Vs 9.66) was not significant (P=0.228). From multivariable logistic regression analysis variables such as level of social support(AOR: 6.24; 95% CI:1.91-20.44), type of treatment(AOR: 0.095; 95% CI: 0.009-0.9), family history of depression (AOR:0.47;95% CI:0.29-0.75) and presence of diabetic complication(AOR: 3.22; 95% CI:1.97-5.27) were significantly associated factors at a P-value of<0.05 and a 95% CI.

Conclusion: . The overall prevalence of depression was un acceptably high and showed that more than half (54.27%) of DM patients struggle to live with depression and its bad consequences. According to the output from multivariable logistic regression analysis, poor level of social support and having diabetic complications were found to be risk factors for depression. Conversely, not having family history of depression and taking oral hypoglycemic agents were proven to be protective factors of depression.

Key Words:Depression, Diabetes Mellitus, oral hypoglycemic agent, insulin,

Abbreviations and Acronyms

- AOR-Adjusted Odds Ratio
- BMI- Body Mass Index
- CI- Confidence Interval
- COR-Crud Odds Ratio
- DM- Diabetes Mellitus
- FMOH- Federal Ministry of Health
- IDF-International Diabetes Federation
- Menelik IIIH- Minilik II Hospital
- MOH- Ministry of Health
- Ms Excel- Microsoft Excel
- NCD- Non-Communicable Disease
- OSSS-3 – Oslo Social Support Scale
- PHQ-9 - Patient Health Questionnaire-9

- SD- Standard Deviation
- SPSS- Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
- T1DM- Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus
- T2DM- Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus
- WHO- World Health Organization
- Vs – Versus
- ZMH- Zewuditu Memorial Hospital

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a major non-communicable disease (NCD) with a significant global health and economic impact. It is a metabolic disorder characterized by the body's inability to properly regulate blood glucose levels due to inadequate insulin production or insulin resistance. This leads to persistent hyperglycemia, which, if left untreated, can lead to serious complications such as cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, and nephropathy (1). The global burden of non-communicable diseases, including diabetes, is significant and affects both high- and low-income countries. In 2021, the global prevalence of diabetes in adults is estimated to be 10.5%, with type 2 diabetes accounting for approximately 90% of all cases(1). The International Diabetes Federation(IDF) predicts that this prevalence will increase by 46% by 2045, highlighting the urgent need of effective prevention and management strategies(2). In Ethiopia, the prevalence of diabetes is estimated to be between 2% and 6.5%(3, 4).

Due to the long duration of treatment and the chronic nature of the disease, a significant proportion of DM patients suffer from depression after diagnosis. Depression is a common mental disorder characterized by persistent unhappiness and a lack of interest in daily activities. The global prevalence of depression is about 35.1% of adults (1), and the estimated prevalence of depression among diabetic patients in Ethiopia is 39.73%, and a subgroup analysis showed that it is 52.9% in Addis Ababa (5). Several lines of evidence suggest a bi-directional relationship between diabetes and depression, highlighting the complex interaction between these two conditions. It is noted that people with diabetes are twice as likely to develop depression than those without diabetes. This increased susceptibility can be attributed to the chronic nature of diabetes, which requires ongoing self-management, life style adjustments and the psychological burden of dealing with a long-term condition (1). Conversely, depression itself is a significant risk factor for the

development of diabetes. Some meta-analyses have shown that patients with major depressive disorder are more likely to develop type 2 diabetes compared to the general population. Depression can lead to unhealthy life styles such as unhealthy diet, physical inactivity and smoking, which are known risk factors for diabetes(6). In addition, depression can lead to changes in the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenalaxis and increase inflammatory markers, contributing to insulin resistance and impaired glucose metabolism. As a result, these people tend to have a reduced quality of life and a higher likelihood of developing diabetes related complications such as cardio-vascular disease and neuropathy, and the presence of depression in diabetic patients is associated with an increased mortality rate. The psychological distress and physiological effects of depression can exacerbate diabetes symptoms and complications, leading to poor health outcomes.

Evidences suggest the importance of early detection and integrated treatment approaches to effectively treat both conditions, improving the overall prognosis and quality of life of those affected. Several lines of evidence suggest a bi-directional relationship between diabetes and depression: Diabetes patients are twice as likely to develop depression as non-diabetics. In contrast, depression increases the risk of diabetes and impairs daily self-management. Diabetes patients with depression have poor glycemic control, a lower quality of life, and an increased risk of diabetes complications and thus a higher mortality rate(7, 8). The estimated prevalence of depression among diabetic patients in Ethiopia is 39.73%, and subgroup analysis shows that it is 52.9% in Addis Ababa (5). The World Health Organization (WHO) affirms lifestyle change as the main means of preventing and managing DM. It also recommends early treatment for both type 1 and uncontrolled type 2 DM to avoid complications.

The Federal Ministry of Health(FMOH) has published a guideline on how to manage DM and it clearly stated that a multi-disciplinary team should be involved to deliver best care for patients in which the center of the team is diabetic patients. It also describes the function of each tier system in managing diabetes. Starting from health post where clinical diagnosis are done up to tertiary hospitals where sub-specialty management is given (9).Understanding the prevalence of depression among diabetic patients using insulin versus oral hypoglycemic medications can inform treatment strategies and improve patient outcomes. This study aims to compare the prevalence of depression between these two medication groups in Addis Ababa public hospitals.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Diabetes Mellitus (DM), particularly type 2 diabetes, is a major global health issue. The global prevalence of diabetes among adults stands at 10.5%, and this is projected to increase by 46% by 2045. Alongside diabetes, depression is a common comorbidity that significantly impacts patients' quality of life and disease management(4). On a global scale, the interplay between diabetes and depression is well-documented. A study highlights that individuals with type 2 diabetes are at an increased risk of developing depression. The meta-analysis revealed that diabetes doubles the odds of experiencing depressive symptoms compared to non-diabetic individuals. The prevalence of depression in diabetes patients is influenced by various factors, including the chronic stress of managing a long-term condition, lifestyle changes, and the direct physiological effects of diabetes on brain function(6). Another Systemic review and metaanalysis further emphasize the significant burden of depression among diabetic patients. It also compared the prevalence of depression in individuals with type 1 and type 2 diabetes to those without diabetes. The findings indicated that both types of diabetes are associated with a higher prevalence of depression, with type 2 diabetes patients exhibiting a particularly high prevalence. This highlights the need for integrated healthcare approaches that address both physical and mental health needs of diabetic patients (10).

Regionally, the burden of diabetes and depression varies, with developing countries experiencing a rapid increase in prevalence. Studies in various regions have reported high rates of comorbid depression among diabetic patients. For instance, a study conducted in Southwest Ethiopia reported a significant prevalence of depression among diabetic patients attending public hospitals. The study found that nearly one-third of diabetic patients experienced depressive symptoms, which were associated with factors such as poor glycemic control, complications from diabetes, and lack of social support (11). In Ethiopia, diabetes prevalence ranges between 2% and 6.5% (4). The burden of comorbid depression among diabetic patients is a critical public health concern. The national guidelines by the Ministry of Health (MOH) and the Addis Ababa Health Bureau emphasize the importance of managing non-communicable diseases, including diabetes and its complications (12).

However, the integration of mental health services into diabetes care remains inadequate. Ebrahim et al. (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study in Eastern Ethiopia and found a notable prevalence of depression among diabetic outpatients. Similar findings were reported in Southwest Ethiopia, where depression was

prevalent among diabetes patients and associated with factors like poor self-care, complications, and socioeconomic challenges (11). These findings underscore the importance of addressing mental health alongside diabetes management to improve patient outcomes.

The presence of depression in DM has been associated with significant negative impact in self-care, glycemic control, health outcomes and quality of life. According to a meta-analysis from 43 studies depression was significantly associated with poor adherence to DM treatment regimen (13). Scholars agreed that, patients with higher depression had lower adherence to general diet recommendations, specific dietary behaviors such as fruits and vegetables consumption, less exercise and poorer foot care at follow-up (14). Depression also had a significant negative impact on poor glycemic control in both types of diabetes according to a metaanalysis from 24 studies with a small to moderate effect size (15). Similarly, diabetes related symptoms were amplified (16); and higher levels of diabetic complications such as retinopathy, macrovascular complications, nephropathy, neuropathy and sexual dysfunction were occurred (17, 18).

Nationally, Ethiopia has implemented several interventional programs and guidelines to manage non-communicable diseases, including diabetes. The Ministry of Health (MOH) and the Addis Ababa Health Bureau have outlined strategies for the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of diabetes and its complications (12). These programs emphasize the importance of early detection, lifestyle modifications, and the use of medications to manage blood glucose levels. Despite these efforts, the management of diabetes in Ethiopia faces several challenges. The availability of healthcare resources, including medications and trained healthcare professionals, is limited, particularly in rural areas. Additionally, the integration of mental health services into diabetes care is often inadequate, leading to underdiagnosis and undertreatment of comorbid conditions such as depression.

1.3. Justifications of the study

In Ethiopia, scholars reported a high prevalence of depression, ranging from 21.3% to 48.9%, among DM patients which may result in significant negative impact in self-care, glycemic control, health outcomes and quality of life. In spite of this huge gap, only some studies were conducted in Ethiopia on the prevalence of depression among DM patients even though they are limited specifically in selected study area. Additionally no study was found in Ethiopia focused on comparing the prevalence of depression among insulin and oral hypoglycemic agent users. Therefore, the aim of this study was to determine the

prevalence of depression and associated factors among adult diabetic patients treated with insulin and oral hypoglycemic medications in public hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

1.4. Significance of the study

This study will tackle a critical gap by determining the prevalence of depression among diabetic patients treated with insulin and oral hypoglycemic medications in Addis Ababa. Unveiling this prevalence is essential for developing targeted interventions that effectively manage both diabetes and mental health conditions.

By focusing on this specific subgroup, this study will be valuable for policymakers and planners since it will offer vital data to inform policy decisions, strategic planning, and resource allocation. The findings from this research will also be useful for Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) and the Addis Ababa Health Bureau in planning and mobilizing resources to effectively address the burden of depression among diabetic patients.

Additionally, the study will help prioritize interventions within the context of limited healthcare resources, ensuring efforts are directed where they are most needed. Associations like the Ethiopian Diabetic Association and the Ethiopian Mental Health Disease Association will benefit from this information, allowing them to enhance their advocacy and support efforts. Finally, clinicians and researchers working in this field will find the study valuable as a reference point for future investigations and clinical practices.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Diabetes and depression represent significant health challenges globally, each with far-reaching impacts on individuals' well-being and quality of life. Numerous studies have explained the relationship between these two conditions, highlighting a complex interplay that exacerbates their respective burdens on affected individuals (10). Diabetic patients compared to normal individuals are considered to have a high risk of developing Depression. A study done in 2010 which is a systemic review and analysis, it shows that Diabetic individuals compared to normal people have a 24% risk of developing depression (6). Another systemic review and meta-analysis done on 2022 which compared the prevalence of depression between people with and without Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes also showed that the prevalence of diagnosed

depression or elevated depressive symptoms was significantly higher in people with Type 1 diabetes compared with those without and in Type 2 diabetes compared to those without (10). This literature review synthesizes findings from a range of studies exploring the prevalence, associations, and implications of comorbid diabetes and depression across different populations and settings.

2.2 Prevalence of Depression in Diabetic Mellitus Patients

Globally, several cross-sectional studies have investigated the prevalence of depression among individuals with diabetes, shedding light on the substantial burden of comorbid depression in this population. For instance, a large-scale global study was conducted in Africa, Eurasia, Latin America, Middle East and South Asia among 9865 participants to determine the prevalence of depressive symptoms among type 1 and type 2 DM patients. According to the report of this large scale study, about 30.7% of type 1 and 33.1% of type 2 DM showed depressive symptoms respectively(19). Similarly, an Institutional based cross-sectional study has been conducted in Spain by 2018 among 3443 DM patients. On this study, approximately one-fifth of patients reported to have depression(20).

Additionally, another cross-sectional study was conducted in Korea in 2005. According to this study, about one third (32.4%) of diabetic patients exhibited signs of depression. On this study, participants who were on insulin therapy nearly twice to develop depression compared to those on oral medications (48.0% vs. 27.3%)(21). Similarly another institutional based cross-sectional study was conducted in Vietnam in 2021 among 216 participants. On this study the prevalence of depression among DM patients was 23.2%(22). Besides this, another cross-sectional study done was conducted in Qatar by 2023 among 683 participants. According to this study, about 20% participants diagnosed to have depression(23). Moreover, three cross-sectional studies were conducted in Saudi Arabia in 2020, 2022, and 2024 using 397, 350 and 386 DM patients respectively. Based on the reports of these studies, the prevalences of depression were 37% in 2020, 36.6% in 2022, and 48.2% in 2024(24-26).

The prevalence of depression among DM patients was about two-third (66.5%) according to a cross-sectional study done in Turkey in 2021 among 281 participants(27). Similarly, a cross-sectional study in India in 2016 revealed a high prevalence of depression among type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) patients, with almost 39% diagnosed with depression, indicating a significant mental health burden within this population (28).

Some scholars tried to determine the prevalence of depression among DM patients in different nations in Africa. For instance, a systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in Africa by 2021 with aim of

determining the prevalence of depression among DM patients. This meta-analysis included 20 single studies from different nations in Africa and the pooled prevalence of depression was found to be 40%(29). Similarly, the prevalences of depression were 18% in Malawi(30); 30.4% in Botswana(31); 34.2% Egypt(32) and 73%&87% in two studies in Tanzania(33, 34).

The prevalence of depression among diabetic patients in Ethiopia varies across studies but consistently indicates a substantial mental health burden within this population. According to a systematic review and meta-analysis conducted in 2018, the prevalence of depression among diabetic patients in Ethiopia was approximately 39.73%, with urban areas such as Addis Ababa reporting even higher rates, estimated at 52.9%(5). Another systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in 2023 to determine the pooled prevalence of depression among DM patients. On this meta-analysis a total of 5808 participants from 16 studies were included. On this study, the pooled prevalence of depression among DM patients was 34.61%(35). Similarly, more recent studies conducted in Ethiopia in 2020 and 2021 incorporate these findings, with prevalence rates ranging from 21.3% to 48.9% among diabetic patients attending public hospitals(11, 36-39)

2.3 Factors affecting prevalence of Depression among Diabetic Patients.

2.3.1 socio-demographic factors

Numerous studies have consistently identified socio-demographic variables as a significant predictor of depression among diabetic patients. According to a large scale cross-sectional study conducted in many countries, female sex, and low socioeconomic status was found to be associated with high prevalence of depression compared to their counterparts(19). Similarly, another cross-sectional study was conducted in Spain to determine the association between socio-demographic variables and depression prevalence in DM patients. According to the report of this study, being female and employment status were associated socio-demographic factor(20). Additionally, another cross-sectional study was conducted in Vietnam. According to this study, age under 60 years, and poor economic status were significantly associated factors(22).

In a study done in Qatar, male patients were at higher risk for developing depression compared to their counterparts(23). Similarly three studies were conducted in Saudi Arabia to determine associated factors of depression among DM patients. Based on the reports of these studies, low educational level, poor income, age group and being female diabetic were found to be associated with the occurrence of depression among DM patients(24-26). However, according to another cross-sectional study done in India, significant

association was not found between depression and socio-demographic factors like age, gender, economic status, type of residence, educational level and marital status of participants (28, 30). Socio-demographic factors like sex were also associated with the occurrence of depression among DM patients according to cross-sectional studies conducted in Botswana and Egypt (31, 32).

In Ethiopia, some researchers strived to determine the association between socio-demographic factors and prevalence of depression among DM patients. For instance, a systematic review and meta-analysis included 16 studies found that, older age > 50 years and being women were found to be significantly associated with the occurrence of depression (35). Another study conducted in Ethiopia has reported higher prevalence rates of depression among female diabetic patients, with factors such as social support, chronic illness, and marital status further exacerbating gender disparities in mental health outcomes. In this study women with diabetes appear to be at a higher risk of experiencing depressive symptoms compared to men (11, 40).

Age and marital status have also been implicated as important socio-demographic factors influencing the prevalence of depression among diabetic individuals. Elderly diabetic patients, particularly those over 75 years old, are more vulnerable to experiencing depressive symptoms, as evidenced by studies conducted in Ethiopia. Similarly, individuals who are divorced or widowed tend to exhibit higher rates of depression compared to their married counterparts, suggesting the protective role of social support networks and spousal relationships in mitigating depressive symptoms among diabetic patients (40). Socioeconomic status emerges as a crucial determinant of depression prevalence among diabetic patients, with lower socioeconomic status individuals facing greater mental health challenges. In other studies done in Ethiopia, factors such as income level, education, and occupation play significant roles in developing depression within diabetic populations. Individuals with lower income levels and educational attainment are more likely to experience depressive symptoms, highlighting the intersecting effects of socioeconomic disadvantage and chronic illness burden on mental well-being (11, 36, 40).

2.3.2 Behavioural and social support factors

To the best of my search, only some studies tried to incorporate social and behavioral factors as potential determinants of depression among diabetic population. Two cross-sectional studies were conducted in Spain (22) and Vietnam (20). According to the findings of these studies, mental health status below mean, poor social support and having stress during the past year determined associated factors of depression among DM population. Additionally, three cross-sectional studies were conducted in Saudi Arabia in

2020, 2022, and 2024 using 397, 350 and 386 DM patients respectively. According to the reports of these studies patients with history of any social issue with the family, relatives, or friends were at risk of developing depression compared to those without such history(24-26). Similarly, another cross-sectional study was conducted in Egypt to determine the prevalence of depression and its associated factors. Based on the findings of this study, anxiety or feeling angry or stressed was significantly associated with the occurrence of depression among DM patients (32)

In Ethiopia, two studies were conducted in 2020 and 2023 to see the association between the occurrence of depression among DM patients and associated behavioural and social support factors. On both studies having poor social support(30) or limited social support (35) were found to be significantly associated with prevalence of depression among DM patients.

2.3.3 Clinical characteristics

Some researchers tried to investigate the association between clinical characteristics of DM and the prevalence of depression. For instance, according to a large-scale global study conducted in Africa, Eurasia, Latin America, Middle East and South Asia having comorbidity with DM was found significantly associated with the prevalence of depression(19). Similarly, Two cross-section studies were conducted in Spain and Korea. According to these studies, presence of diabetic complications, type of treatment(21), fair or poor self-reported health status, and low physical activity were significantly associated risk factors for depression(20). In another study done in Vietnam, unstable or part-time work, poor treatment adherence to type 2 diabetes mellitus, and engaging in heavy physical activity or physical activity less than three days per week were found to be associated with the occurrence of depression among DM patients(22). Additionally, type of treatment was also associated with the prevalence of depression according to a cross-sectional study done in Qatar(23).

Furthermore, according to three cross-sectional studies done in Saudi Arabia, presence of complications, like thyroid dysfunction; neuropathy, nephropathy, and libido were found to be associated with the occurrence of depression. Additionally, type of DM, type of treatment, duration of DM, family history of DM were also found to be significant associated factors for the prevalence of depression among DM patients(24-26).

Moreover, according to the researches conducted in Botswana and Egypt, presence of diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy, diabetic foot ulcers, impotence, being on insulin therapy and being a current smoker were found significantly associated factors of the occurrence of DM(31, 32). Type of DM was also

associated with the prevalence of depression according to a cross-sectional study done in Tirunesh-Beijing general hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia(30). However, based on the report of another cross-sectional study done in India, association was not found between depression and duration of diabetes, HbA1c level and BMI of participants(28, 30).

In general, in this literature review, it is found that the prevalence of depression range from 20% in Qatar to 87% in Tanzania and significantly associated factors were age, sex, low educational level, poor income, marital status, occupation, history of any social issue with the family, relatives, or friends, anxiety or feeling angry or stressed, having poor or limited social support, having comorbidity, fair or poor self-reported health status, and low physical activity, poor treatment adherence, engaging in heavy physical activity, type of DM, type of treatment, duration of DM, and family history of DM .

2.4 Conceptual Framework

The prevalence of Depression among Diabetic Patients can be seen from different perspectives as shown in the conceptual framework below. This conceptual framework was developed by reviewing different literatures (19-26).

Clinical characteristics

- Duration of diabetes,
- Comorbidity,
- Type of diabetes, family history of diabetes, and
- Family history of depression
- Type of treatment

Socio-Demographic factors

- Age,
- Sex,
- Marital status,
- Occupation,
- Level of education, and
- Place of residence

Behavioral and social support factors

- Alcohol consumption,
- Cigarette smoking,
- Khat chewing,
- Physical activity,
- Living condition,
- and social support

Prevalence of depression among DM patients

Figure 1- conceptual framework for the research on assessing the prevalence of depression among Insulin and oral Hypoglycemic medication users.

3. Objectives

3.1 General Objective

- The general objective of this study was to determine the prevalence of depression and associated factors among adult diabetic patients using insulin Vs oral hypoglycemic medications in public hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

3.2 Specific Objectives:

- To compare the difference in prevalence of depression among adult diabetic patients taking insulin and oral hypoglycemic medications.
- To determine associated factors of depression among Insulin and oral hypoglycemic user Diabetic patients.

4. Methods and Materials

4.1. Study area and period

This study was conducted in 3 public hospitals located in Addis Ababa (Tirunesh Beijing Hospital, Zewditu Memorial Hospital, Menelik II Hospital). All the mentioned hospitals deliver comprehensive Diabetic mellitus follow-up and Treatment. Addis Ababa is the capital city of Ethiopia which is located in the central part of the country. It is located on a well-watered plateau surrounded by hills and mountains in the geographic center of the country. The city was founded in 1887 and was named Addis Ababa(41). It is geographically located at the heart of the nation, 9.02’N latitude and 38.45’E longitude. Its average altitude is 2,400 meter above sea level; and the city occupies a total of 540 sq. km. In 2023, there would be 5,461,000 people living in Addis Ababa. The city has 13 functional public hospitals that give service to the community from those 6 are under the region of Addis Ababa while the remaining are federal government hospitals(42). The study was conducted from October, 1 to November,30 /2024.

4.2 Study Design

A comparative cross-sectional study design was conducted among diabetic patients in three public general hospitals. The study participants were both Insulin and Oral hypoglycemic medication Users.

4.3 Population

4.3.1 Source Population

The source population were all DM patients who have regular follow-up in public hospitals located in Addis Ababa.

4.3.2 Study Population

The study population were all DM patients in selected public hospitals, who have follow-up appointments during the data collection period.

4.4. Illigblity Criteria

4.4.1. Inclusion Criteria

- DM patients aged >18years who have follow-up visits during data collection time and followed for at least 1 year were included in this study.

4.4.2. Exclusion Criteria

- This study excluded DM patients diagnosed with any severe cognitive impairment that would hinder participation (e.g., dementia). Similarly patients diagnosed as having any Psychiatric Disorder that hinder to give informed written consent were excluded.
- Additionally, DM patients currently participating in another similar study were also excluded from this study since it might result in data bias.

4.5 Sample size determination

To determine sample size, single population proportion formula was used taking into account a study conducted in Eastern Ethiopia with a prevalence(P) of 48.9%(43) using the following formula.

$$n = \frac{(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 \times p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ = the critical value of the normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (e.g. for a confidence level of 95%, α is 0.05 and the critical value is 1.96), d = the margin of error, p = the prevalence of depression among DM patients from previous study which is 48.9% in Eastern Ethiopia (43).

$$n = (1.96)^2 (0.489 * 0.511) / (0.05)^2 = 383.9 = 384$$

Finally, a 10% additional sample was added for non-respondents and the final sample size was 422.

Then, sample size for the 2nd objective was calculated by using double proportion formula as shown in the table below using EPI-info-7.

Table 1. The sample size calculation to assess the prevalence of depression among DM patients and associated factors in Addis Ababa public hospitals.

Variable	Proportion		Total sample size
	P1	P2	
Sex	26.9	21.9	302
Duration of illness	14.7	34.2	70
Current khat chowing	30.4	18.4	26

Keys: P1 is the proportion of exposed DM patients with the outcome, P2 is the proportion of non-exposed DM patients with the outcome, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is taking CI of 95%, and Z_{β} is 80% power and, r is the ratio of exposed to non-exposed DM patients 1:1. While the sample sizes of the objectives compared to each other, the single population sample size was considered for data collection since it gave the maximum number. Consequently, 302 participants were the total sample size for the 2nd objective. However, the sample size calculated for the 1st objective was larger compared to the calculated sample size for the 2nd objective. Hence, took the larger sample size to improve the quality and reliability of the results. so the final sample was 422.

4.6 Sampling Technique

There are 6 General public hospitals under Addis Ababa city administration. From these hospitals, Gandhi Memorial Hospital gives only maternal and child health service, thus was excluded from the study. From remaining 5 general hospitals 3 hospitals were randomly selected for this study. Study participants for each hospital were proportionally allocated based on the number of monthly DM patient visits of each hospital. For each selected hospital, participants were selected using systematic random sampling technique and the total sampling frame of each hospital was divided by the final sample size to determine sampling interval (K). The 1st participant from the interval was selected by simple random sampling technique.

Figure 2; Shows schematic presentation of sample hospitals that will be used for assessing the prevalence of Depression among insulin and Oral hypoglycemic medication users in public hospitals Addis Ababa Ethiopia.

4.7 Study Variables

4.7.1 Dependent Variable

- Prevalence of Depression.

4.7.2 Independent Variables were:

- **Socio-demographic variables:** such as age, sex, marital status, occupation, level of education, and place of residence
- **Clinical characteristics:** such as duration of diabetes, comorbidity, type of diabetes, family history of diabetes, family history of depression, and type of treatment

- **Behavioral and social support factors:** such as alcohol consumption, cigarette smoking, khat chewing, physical activity, living conditions, and social support

4.8. Data collection tools

A questionnaire adopted from a previous study was used(44). The questionnaire assessed socio-demographic & socio-economic status, clinical characteristics, and behavioral and social support factors. Additionally, the questionnaire had the PHQ-9 components to assess the depression status of the study participants. This depression scale questionnaire has 9 questions with a score of “0 to and a total score of 0 to 27”. The prevalence of depression was dichotomized into "depression present" or "depression absent" based on the depression assessment tool(PHQ-9). If the total depression score is below 5, it is considered as depression absent and otherwise considered as depression present. The questionnaire was translated into the local language (Amharic) and back-translated to English and back to Amharic by independent translators to maintain consistency. Data collectors also reviewed the medical records of the study population.

4.9. Data collection procedure:

Data were collected by 3 BSc Nurse including review of patient charts and the supervisors and the principal investigator followed the overall data collection process. The supervisor and data collectors were trained for a full day regarding data collection procedures including eligibility criteria in selecting DM patients and their medical records. The supervisor checked the collected data for completeness in daily basis.

4.11. Quality assurance:

To maintain research quality, clear, specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound objectives were formulated. Additionally, appropriate research design; clear sampling strategy that ensures representativeness and minimizes bias; and appropriate statistical methods to determine sample size were used. Furthermore, validated and reliable data collection was also prepared. As an additional data quality measure, a pretest was done at Black Lion Specialized Hospital by taking 5% of the sample size. After the pretest, necessary modifications were made especially in some parts of the questionnaire.

Data collectors and a supervisor were trained for one full day about the tool, the ethical aspect of the study, and the overall data collection process. On a daily basis, the supervisor audited the data extraction from the patient's medical chart daily.

4.11 Operational Definitions

Depression: from PHQ9 evaluation will be

- ❖ <5: No depression
 - ❖ 5-9: Mild depression
 - ❖ 10-14: Moderate depression
 - ❖ 15-19: Moderately severe depression
 - ❖ 20-27: Severe depression(44).
 - ❖ Prevalence of depression was dichotomized in to "depression present" or "depression absent" based on the depression assessment tool. If the total depression score is below 5, it was considered as depression absent and otherwise considered as depression present
- Current use and ever use of a substance: is using of at least one substance in the last 3 months and once in a lifetime, respectively.
 - Social support is classified into three categories based on OSSS-3; “poor social support” if a sum score was 3–8, “moderate social support” if a sum score was 9–11, and “strong social support” if a sum score was 12–14 and Social support is said to be good if the score is from 9-14(45).
 - Good glycemic control: a fasting blood glucose level less than or equals 130 mg/dL(46).
 - Poor glycemic control: a fasting blood glucose level greater than 130 mg/dL(46).

4.12. Data Management and Analysis

The collected data were checked, coded, entered and cleaned using Epi info 7. Then this data were exported to Ms-Excel and then to SPSS version 26 software for analysis. Descriptive statistics for categorical variables was presented in the form of frequencies and percentages, and mean and standard deviation(SD) used to describe continuous variables. The model fitness was assessed using the Hosmer-Lemeshow test and multicollinearity among independent variables was also evaluated using the variance inflation factor (VIF) test. The dependent variable (prevalence of depression) was dichotomized in to "depression present" or "depression absent" based on the depression assessment tool.

Then, bivariate logistic regression analysis was performed for each independent variable regarding the presence of depression among DM patients. At this stage, independent variables with a p-value of <0.25 were selected for multivariate logistic regression analysis. Finally, an adjusted odd ratio (AOR) with 95% confidence interval was used to identify associated variables for depression among DM patients, and p-values < 0.05 was used to declare statistical significance.

4.13. Ethical Consideration

An ethical clearance for this study obtained from the institutional review board of Gamby Medical School. Ethical approval letter was also obtained from Addis Ababa Health office. After that, a written permission letter to access patient's charts obtained from responsible body of each institution. Informed written consent was obtained from each participant. The consent form included information on the right to withdraw at any time without any reason (including withdrawing data already provided), assured that participant were de identified, clarity of ownership of the data (participants own their raw data, researchers own the analysis data), their right to access to their data, the right to ask for more information, and information of the complaint process (contact details of the researcher). The data generated from the medical records of DM patients were also de-identified in order to maintain privacy and anonymity of the study participants. This study adhered to the ethical principles stipulated in the Helsinki Declaration of research in human subjects. Finally the collected data were stored in strongly protected computer with strong passwords.

5. Result

5.1. Socio-demographic characteristic

A total of 422 participants were included in this study with a response rate of 100%. More than half of the study participants were males (51.4%), and the majority (77.3%) of them were urban dwellers. The age of participants ranged from 18 to 78 years with a median age of 52 years. Approximately one-third (32.7%) of participants were single, and about 44.8% and 14.5% of participants were married and divorced respectively. Regarding educational status, nearly one-fourth (23%) of participants cannot read and write and, less than half (45.7%) of participants had secondary school or above level of education (Table 2).

Table 2. shows distribution of socio-demographic variables among DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (422).

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	217	51.4
	Female	205	48.6
Residence	Urban	326	77.3
	Rural	96	22.7
Marital status	Married	189	44.8
	Single	138	32.7
	Divorced	61	14.5
	Widowed	34	8.1
Educational status	Cannot read and write	97	23.0
	Read and write only	101	23.9
	Primarily school	31	7.3
	Secondary school and above	193	45.7
Occupational status	Governmental employer	182	43.1
	Privet worker	117	27.7
	Merchant	84	19.9
	Farmer	39	9.2

5.2. Clinical related characteristics

On this study, participants followed DM clinic for a minimum of 1 year and a maximum of 35 years with a mean follow-up time of 8.4 years. Majority, 304(72%) of participants had type 2 diabetes mellitus and treated with oral hypoglycemic agents (37%), Insulin (26.5%) and both (36.5%). Eventhough treatment modalities different according to the patient and type of DM, the participants fasting blood glucose level ranged from 67 to 309mg/dl with a mean fasting blood suger of 118.8 mg/dl and one fourth(25.8%) of participants had uncontrolled blood glucose and about 38% of participants experienced DM complications once at least once in their life time such as hypoglycemia (7.8%), nephropathy (6.4%), neuropathy (4%), Vascular complications (3.1%), and retinopathy (1.7%). Regarding comorbidity, majority (62.6%) of participants had at least one form of Comorbid disease including renal disease (18%), heart disease(16.1%) and hypertension(8.1%). On this study about 33.4% and 41.2% of participants had family history of DM and depression respectively (Table 3).

Table 3. Shows distribution of clinical and treatment related variables among DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (n=422).

Variables	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Type of DM	Type 1	118	28.0
	Type 2	304	72.0
Type of treatment	Oral hypoglycemic agent	156	37.0
	Insulin therapy	112	26.5
	Both	154	36.5
Glycemic control	Good	313	74.2
	Poor	109	25.8
Do you currently/ever have DM complication(s)	Yes	163	38.6
	No	259	61.4
Type of complication	Hypoglycemic	33	7.8
	Renal	27	6.4
	Neuropathy	17	4.0
	Vascular	13	3.1
	ophthalmologic	7	1.7
Is there any comorbidity	Yes	264	62.6
	No	158	37.4
Type of comorbidity	Renal disease	76	18.0
	Heart disease	68	16.1
	Hypertension	34	8.1
	Other	21	5.0
Family history of DM	Yes	141	33.4
	No	281	66.6
Past history of depression	Yes	126	29.9
	No	296	70.1
Family history of depression	Yes	174	41.2
	No	248	58.8

5.3. Behavioral factors

On this study, about 22% of participants were active smokers and 36% participants had a history of smoking in the past. Similarly, about 44% of participants had a history of alcohol drinking and currently, more than half (51.7%) drunk alcohol. Regarding to the use of Shisha and khat, about 7.3% used Shisha in their life time and 33.6% of participants chew khat with in 12 months (Table 4).

Table 4. Distribution of behavioral factors among DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (422).

Variables	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Currently smoking status	Yes	93	22.0
	No	329	78.0
History of smoking	Yes	152	36.0
	No	270	64.0
History of alcohol within the past 12 months	Yes	218	51.7
	No	204	48.3
History of ever use alcohol	Yes	187	44.3
	No	235	55.7
History of Khat within the past 12 months	Yes	142	33.6
	No	280	66.4
History of ever use Shisha	Yes	31	7.3
	No	391	92.7

5.4. Social support factors

On this study the participant social support was assessed using OSLO social support tool (OSSS-3). The participants overall social support score ranged from 4 to 14 with a median score of 10. Majority (84.6%) of participants live with family (Table 5) and almost two-third (66.6%) of participants had good social support (Figure 3).

Table 5. shows frequency distributions of social support scale using OSSS-3 among DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (422).

Variable	Category	Frequency(n)	Percentage%
Number of people so close to you during serious personal problems	None	89	21.1
	1 or 2	106	25.1
	3-5	122	28.9
	More than 5	105	24.9
Level of concern people show in what you are doing.	No concern and interest	48	11.4
	Little concern and interest	60	14.2
	Uncertain	80	19.0
	some concern and interest	148	35.1
	A lot of concern and interest	86	20.4
Easiness to get practical help from neighbors	Very difficult	45	10.7
	Difficult	126	29.9
	Possible	81	19.2
	Easy	121	28.7
	Very easy	49	11.6
Social support level	Poor	141	33.4
	Good	281	66.6
Living circumstance	With family	357	84.6
	Alone	65	15.4

Figure 3. Shows the overall social support level of DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (422).

5.5. Prevalence of depression among DM treated with insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic agents

Depression was assessed by using a nine 4-scale questioner (PHQ-9). According to this research data, the overall depression scale score of participants ranged from 2 to 26 with a mean±SD score of 9.44±7.8. On this study, the prevalence of depression showed variability among DM participants taking oral hypoglycemic agents (44.9%) and insulin users (63.4%) even though the difference in their mean depression scale score (8.54 Vs 9.66) was not significant (P=0.228)(Table 6) and the overall prevalence of depression was 54.27% (95% CI:49.4%-59.1%) (Figure 4)

Table 6. Shows the response of participants towards PHQ-9

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Little interest or pleasure in doing things	Not at all	213	50.5
	Several days	111	26.3
	More than half the day	40	9.5
	Nearly every day	58	13.7
Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless?	Not at all	188	44.5
	Several days	112	26.5
	More than half the day	81	19.2
	Nearly every day	41	9.7
Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	Not at all	181	42.9
	Several days	143	33.9
	More than half the day	43	10.2

	Nearly every day	55	13.0
Feeling tired or having little energy	Not at all	147	34.8
	Several days	150	35.5
	More than half the day	50	11.8
	Nearly every day	75	17.8
Poor appetite or overeating	Not at all	160	37.9
	Several days	149	35.3
	More than half the day	45	10.7
	More than half the day	68	16.1
Feeling bad about yourself or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	Not at all	145	34.4
	Several days	150	35.5
	More than half the day	53	12.6
	Nearly every day	74	17.5
Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	Not at all	171	40.5
	Several days	126	29.9
	More than half the day	61	14.5
	Nearly every day	64	15.2
Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed or the opposite being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual?	Not at all	115	27.3
	Several days	167	39.6
	More than half the day	65	15.4
	Nearly every day	75	17.8
Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself in some way?	Not at all	165	39.1
	Several days	118	28.0
	More than half the day	85	20.1
	Nearly every day	54	12.8
Depression among insulin users	Yes	71	63.4
	No	41	36.6
Depression among oral hypoglycemic agent users	Yes	70	44.9
	No	86	55.1

Figure 4. Shows the prevalence of depression among DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (422).

5.6. Associated factors of depression among patients with Diabetes mellitus

To check the association between independent variables and dependent variable all the variables were tested under bivariate logistic regression. About eleven variables including occupational status, the number of close people for the patient during serious personal problems, the amount of concern people show for the patient, easiness to get practical help from neighbors, Length of time since the diagnosis of DM, Smoking history, the level of social support, the level of glycemic control, type of DM, type of treatment, family history of depression and diabetic complications showed association with depression at a p-value <0.25 . These variables were selected for multivariable logistic regression analysis and only four variables such as level of social support, type of treatment, family history of depression and presence of diabetic complication were significantly associated variables at a P-value of <0.05 and a 95% CI.

According to this study, diabetic patients with poor level of social support were 6.2 times more likely to develop depression compared to participants with good social support (AOR: 6.24; 95% CI: 1.91-20.44). Similarly, diabetic patients with complications were 3.2 times more likely to have depression than their counterparts (AOR: 3.22; 95% CI: 1.97-5.27). On the other hand, compared to diabetic patients with a family history of depression, participants with no family history of depression were 53% less likely to develop depression (AOR: 0.47; 95% CI: 0.29-0.75). Moreover, diabetic patients treated with oral hypoglycemic agents were about 90% less likely to develop depression compared to patients treated with injectable insulin (AOR: 0.095; 95% CI: 0.009-0.9) (Table 6).

Table 7. Shows bivariate and multivariate analysis to identifies associated factors of depression among DM patients using insulin and/or oral hypoglycemic medication in selected public hospitals of Addis Ababa, 2024 (422).

Variable	Category	Depression		COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)	P-value
		Yes	No			
Occupational status	Farmer	16	23	1	1	
	Governmental employer	111	71	2.25(1.11-4.54)	0.51(0.19-1.34)	0.17
	Privet worker	56	61	1.32(0.63-2.75)	1.31(0.68-2.53)	0.41
	Merchant	46	38	1.74(0.81-3.75)	0.92(0.45-1.86)	0.81
# of close people for serious personal problems?	None	61	28	1	1	
	1 or 2	66	40	0.76(0.42-1.37)	0.92(0.31-2.71)	0.88
	3-5	54	68	0.36(0.21-.65)	0.79(0.32-1.92)	0.60
	More than 5	48	57	0.39(0.21-.70)	0.54(0.26-1.10)	0.09
How much concern do people show in what you are doing?	No concern and interest	36	12	4.59(2.10-10.04)	1.85(0.24-14.18)	0.55
	Little concern and interest	51	9	8.67(3.78-19.87)	4.06(0.73-22.51)	0.11
	Uncertain	47	33	2.18(1.17-4.05)	1.98(0.62-6.36)	0.25
	some concern and interest	61	87	1.07(0.62-1.84)	1.10(0.50-2.39)	0.81
	A lot of concern and interest	34	52	1	1	
How easy is it to get practical help from neighbors if you should need it?	Very difficult	37	8	6.71(2.59-17.40)	1.65(.23-12.09)	0.62
	Difficult	84	42	2.90(1.47-5.72)	1.84(0.46-7.35)	0.39
	Possible	40	41	1.42(0.69-2.90)	2.01(0.60-5.88)	0.20
	Easy	48	73	0.95(0.49-1.88)	0.97(0.41-2.32)	0.94
	Very easy	20	29	1	1	
Length of time(years) since DM diagnosis	-	-	-	1.04(1.01-1.08)	1.03(0.98-1.08)	0.19
In the past, did you ever smoke any tobacco products?	Yes	103	49	2.40(1.59-3.64)	1.78(0.68-4.62)	0.24
	No	126	144	1	1	
Social support level	Poor	114	27	6.10(3.76-9.87)	6.24(1.91-20.44)	0.01
	Good	115	166	1	1	
Social support score				0.76(0.71-0.82)	1.24(0.87-1.78)	0.24
Glycemic control	Good	175	138	1.29(0.84-.10)	1.16(0.66-2.03)	0.61
	Poor	54	55	1	1	
Treatment (medication) type	Insulin therapy	71	41	1	1	
	Oral hypoglycemic agent	70	86	0.47(0.29-0.77)	0.095(0.009-0.9)	0.04
	Both	88	66	1.64(1.05-2.57)	5.57(0.54-57.21)	0.15
Type of DM	Type 1	72	46	1.47(0.95-2.26)	.20(.02-2.04)	0.17
	Type 2	157	147	1	1	
Family history of depression	Yes	75	99	1	1	
	No	154	94	0.46(0.31-.69)	0.47(0.29-0.75)	0.01
Do you ever/currently have any known diabetic complication	Yes	116	47	3.19(2.10-4.85)	3.22(1.97-5.27)	0.01
	No	113	146	1	1	

6. Discussion

In this study, a total of 422 DM patients were recruited for data collection with a response rate of 100 percent with the overall goal of determining the prevalence and associated factors of depression among insulin Vs oral hypoglycemic user DM patients. The prevalence of depression was different among DM participants taking oral hypoglycemic agents (44.9%) and insulin users (63.4%) even though the difference in their mean depression scale score (8.54 Vs 9.66) was not significant ($P=0.228$). This finding was higher in both groups compared to a cross-sectional study done in Korea, (48% among insulin users vs. 27.3% among oral hypoglycemic agent users) (21). In this study, the overall prevalence of depression was 54.27% (95% CI:49.4%-59.1%), this was unacceptably high and showed that more than half of DM patients struggle to live with depression and its bad consequences including poor adherence, poor self-care, poor glycemic control, poor health outcomes and so on. This study was in line with another single institution-based study done in Addis Ababa with a prevalence rate of 52.9%(5).

The prevalence of depression in this study was higher than a global large-scale study done in Africa, Eurasia, Latin America, the Middle East, and South Asia among 9865 participants with an overall 30.7% and 33.1% prevalence of depression among type 1 and type 2 DM respectively(19). Similarly, the prevalence of depression in this study was also higher than studies done in Spain(20%)(20), Vietnam(23.2%) (22), Qatar(20%) (23), and India (39%) (28). The justification for variation might be in developed countries, the care of chronic disease might be well integrated with the care of mental health including depression. This might affect the prevalence of depression to lower in those countries.

Moreover, the prevalence of depression reported on this study was also higher than three studies conducted in Saudi Arabia in 2020, 2022, and 2024 with the prevalences of depression 37% in 2020, 36.6% in 2022, and 48.2% in 2024. The possible explanation for higher prevalence in this study might be the health care set-up and quality in Ethiopia might be uncomfortable and poor quality relative to Saudi Arabia. Additionally, the prevalence of depression among DM patients in this study was higher than studies done in some countries in Africa such as 18% in Malawi(30); 30.4% in Botswana(31); 34.2% in Egypt(32). In these countries, the health literacy level of the people and health care quality of the government might be scaled up, this might contribute to a lower level of depression in their DM population. This study also reported a higher prevalence of depression compared to two meta-analyses done in Ethiopia with pooled

prevalence of 39.73%, and 34.61%(35). The pooled prevalence might be affected by many studies done in rural parts of Ethiopia with lower prevalence of depression and this might contributed to lower level of depression prevalence.

However, the prevalence of depression on this study was lower than in a cross-sectional study done in Turkey with a depression prevalence of 66.5% (27). The possible justification of the higher prevalence of depression Turkey DM population might be the lifestyle and long time work hours among the Turkey population which might exacerbate depressive symptoms. Similarly, the prevalence of depression among DM patients in this study was lower compared to two studies (73%&87%) conducted in Tanzania(33, 34). The justification for this huge difference might be the variation in participant's socio-demography and sample size.

After adjusting for confounding variables, level of social support, type of treatment, family history of depression, and presence of diabetic complications were found to be significantly associated with the prevalence of depression. Based on the report of this study, diabetic patients with poor levels of social support were 6.2 times more likely to develop depression compared to participants with good social support. The scientific explanation for the association is that individuals who feel as if they had support from multiple aspects might have hope and assume a bright future. As a result, the probability of developing depression might be lower compared to participants with poor social support.

Even if only some studies tried to incorporate social and behavioral factors as potential determinants of depression among the diabetic population, this study was supported by two studies conducted in Ethiopia (30,35). Similarly, this finding was supported by different cross-sectional studies conducted in Spain(22) and Vietnam (20), Egypt (32) and three cross-sectional studies conducted in Saudi Arabia (24-26).

Regarding DM complications, diabetic patients who faced complications were 3.2 times more likely to have depression than their counterparts (AOR: 3.22; 95% CI:1.97-5.27). The possible scientific explanation for the association between DM complications and depression is understandable. Diabetes mellitus has many long-term complications including retinopathy (blindness), nephropathy (renal failure), and neuropathy that might disable the patient's normal functions. As a result, the patient might have a deficit even for self-care which might lead him to hopelessness and depression at the end. This finding was supported by studies conducted in Korea (21), three studies done in Saudi Arabia(24-26), and two studies conducted in Botswana and Egypt(31, 32). However, the association between diabetic

complications and the occurrence of depression was not found in studies done in Spain (20), Vietnam (22), and Qatar (23).

Moreover, diabetic patients treated with oral hypoglycemic agents were about 90% less likely to develop depression compared to patients treated with injectable insulin (AOR: 0.095; 95% CI: 0.009-0.9).

This finding scientifically explains that participants taking oral hypoglycemic agents are safer from multiple aspects such as side effects; and pain, abnormal muscle distribution & occurrence of wounds on the injection site. As a result, patients taking oral hypoglycemic agents might have a lower chance of developing depression compared to DM patients taking injectable insulin. The finding is supported by studies done in Qatar (23), and 3 studies in Saudi Arabia (24-26). However, this study is contradicted with studies done in Botswana and Egypt (31, 32) which reported that using insulin is protective factor for prevalence of depression. Finally, compared to diabetic patients with a family history of depression, patients with no family history of depression were 53% less likely to develop depression (AOR: 0.47; 95% CI: 0.29-0.75). This is scientifically acceptable that about half of depression cases had genetic linkage to prior family. Therefore, DM patients with genetic linkage of depression in their prior family might have a higher likelihood of developing depression. However, none of studies were incorporated family history of depression as a possible associated factor.

7. Conclusion

The prevalence of depression was different among DM participants taking oral hypoglycemic agents (44.9%) and insulin users (63.4%) even though the difference in their mean depression scale score (8.54 Vs 9.66) was not significant. The overall prevalence of depression was unacceptably high and showed that more than half (54.27%) of DM patients struggle to live with depression and its bad consequences. According to the output from multivariable logistic regression analysis, poor level of social support and having diabetic complications were found to be risk factors for depression. Conversely, not having family history of depression and taking oral hypoglycemic agents were proven to be protective factors of depression.

8. Recommendation

The findings of this study is valuable for different reasons:

For policymakers: the prevalence of depression in this study was found to be very high relative to the national prevalence of depression among the general population. This indicated that there is an urgent need for policies and strategies that guide the integration of chronic diseases like DM and hypertension with mental health illness.

For the Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) and the Addis Ababa Health Bureau:

FMOH) and the Addis Ababa Health Bureaus should mobilize resources to effectively address the burden of depression among diabetic patients.

For Ethiopian Diabetic Association and Ethiopian Mental Health Disease Association:

Based on the findings from this study, the Ethiopian Diabetic Association and the Ethiopian Mental Health Disease Association should use this information to enhance their advocacy and support efforts.

Finally, clinicians and researchers working in this field should use this study as a reference point for future investigations and clinical practices.

9 Limitations of the study

This study, while contributing valuable insights into the prevalence and associated factors of depression among diabetic patients in Addis Ababa public hospitals, is subject to several limitations that warrant consideration when interpreting its findings.

Primarily, the cross-sectional design employed in this research captures data at a single point in time. This inherent characteristic prevents the establishment of definitive cause-and-effect relationships between the identified associated factors and the presence of depression. While associations (e.g., between poor social support and depression) were identified, it remains unclear whether these factors directly precede and cause depression, or if a reverse causality exists, or if both are influenced by unmeasured confounding variables. Consequently, this design limits the ability to infer temporality or to track the natural progression of depression within the diabetic patient population over time.

Secondly, the study's scope was confined to selected public hospitals within Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. This specific geographical and institutional focus, while providing localized insights, may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader diabetic patient population across Ethiopia. The discussion section of this thesis implicitly acknowledges potential influences of the local healthcare context, suggesting that the "health care set-up and quality in Ethiopia might be uncomfortable and poor quality" compared to developed countries. Such contextual differences can influence the reported prevalence rates and associated factors, thus acting as a regional limitation on the external validity of the results.

Thirdly, the methodology likely involved self-reported data for depression assessment, presumably through a standardized tool such as the PHQ-9. While efficient, this reliance on participant self-disclosure can introduce potential biases, including recall bias (inaccurate memory of symptom frequency or severity) or social desirability bias (where participants may underreport symptoms due to societal stigma or a desire to present themselves favorably). These biases could potentially lead to an underestimation or misrepresentation of the true prevalence of depression within the study population.

Finally, despite efforts to control for various factors, there remains a possibility of unmeasured confounding variables that were not included in the analytical model. These unmeasured factors, which could encompass more nuanced psychosocial stressors, the specific duration and severity of diabetic complications beyond basic categorization, or the intricacies of informal support systems not fully captured by the instruments used, might influence the observed relationships between diabetes and depression. Their exclusion could subtly impact the magnitude and significance of the associations identified in this study.

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